

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

D8.1 Regulatory Landscape

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Full Name	Short Name	Beneficiary Number	Role
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	UCD	1	Coordinator
INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE CONTRE LES CANCERS DE L'APPAREIL DIGESTIF	IRCAD	2	Beneficiary
STICHTING E.A.E.S	EAES	3	Beneficiary
EAES SUPPORT BV	S-EAES	3.1	AE
PINTAIL LTD	PT	4	Beneficiary
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH	5	Beneficiary
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	UNITO	6	Beneficiary
ZIEKENHUIS OOST-LIMBURG AUTONOME VERZORGINGSINSTELLING	ZOL	7	Beneficiary
ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO	ARCTUR	8	Beneficiary
STICHTING VUMC	VUMC	9	Beneficiary
THE PENNSYLVANIA STATE UNIVERSITY	PSU	10	Beneficiary
KONVENT DER BARMHERZIGEN BRUDER GRAZ	BBGRAZ	11	Beneficiary

Executive Summary

D8.1 ‘Regulatory Landscape’ provides an overview of the EU legislative framework applicable to the development and evaluation of medical AI devices and describes how the regulatory requirements have been implemented in the CLASSICA project, which aims to develop and clinically validate an AI-based support system for surgery.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) are key EU regulations relevant to the development and validation of the CLASSICA system. Additionally, if the CLASSICA system is placed on market after the general date of application of the AI Act (AIA) (approximately mid-2026), it must comply with this regulation, too.

The GDPR governs the processing of personal data. In the CLASSICA project, partners process data concerning health, such as interoperative videos and biopsy results, for research purposes. Under GDPR, “data concerning health” is a special category of personal data that demands higher protection. The lawful grounds for processing the data vary by partner and include consent and public task, in combination with fulfilling the conditions for processing a special category of data, that is explicit consent or compliance with research exemption provisions. The CLASSICA clinical sites (ZOL, VUmc, and BBGRAZ), ARCTUR (data analytics company) and UCD act as joint controllers, which means that they jointly determine the purposes and means of data processing. They have signed a joint controller agreement, which specifies the parties’ rights and obligations with regard to the processing activities, including data sharing. The CLASSICA partners have implemented GDPR-mandated security measures, such as pseudonymisation and encryption.

The MDR governs the development and evaluation of medical devices, including medical device software. The CLASSICA system qualifies as medical device under the MDR and falls into the risk class IIa (whereby class I is the lowest risk class and class III is the highest risk class). As such, it must undergo a third-party conformity assessment. The requirements of the MDR include, among other things, achieving performance intended by the manufacturer and demonstrating an acceptable benefit-risk ratio in the context of the state-of-the-art. The studies conducted within the CLASSICA project will be used to verify compliance with these requirements. Two CLASSICA studies qualify as clinical investigations under the MDR, that is, studies which involve human subjects and have a purpose of assessing the safety or performance of the medical device. The requirements for clinical investigation under the MDR include preparing study documentation (e.g., investigator’s brochure and clinical investigation plan), obtaining the Member State’s authorisation and informed consent of the study participants, among other things. After completing the clinical evaluation—which includes verifying that clinical data demonstrate compliance with the MDR’s requirements—and fulfilling all other MDR stipulations, the manufacturer can seek the conformity assessment by a notified body. A positive outcome will allow the manufacturer to declare the conformity with the MDR, label the CLASSICA system with a CE mark and place the system on the EU market.

The AIA is a new EU regulation approved by the European Parliament in March 2024 and set to enter into force in mid-2024. The AIA will govern the market entry of AI systems. Medical AI software like the CLASSICA system, which fits the definition of “AI system” in the AIA, must comply with the AIA, if placed on the market after the general date of application of the AI Act (i.e., two years after entry into force). Compliance with the MDR and AIA will be verified through a single conformity assessment procedure by a notified body.

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List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	AI Act
DoA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The aim of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the EU legislative framework applicable to medical AI devices with a focus on the specific context of the CLASSICA project, which aims to develop and clinically validate an AI-based support system for surgery. This work contributes to a broader objective of the WP8, namely “to explore legal, ethical, and liability questions raised by AI-assisted surgery, (including video databanks), thereby addressing concerns surgeons may have to use such systems”, as specified in the Description of Action (DoA).

It should be stressed that this document does not provide an exhaustive or binding description of the legal requirements applicable throughout the development and commercialisation of the medical AI systems. This “roadmap” serves as an information-only tool. Its use does not guarantee compliance with the relevant regulatory requirements. The task of ensuring the compliance of the CLASSICA project activities with relevant regulations lies within the responsibility of each of the CLASSICA partners who process personal data and develop and evaluate the CLASSICA software. The WP8 team does not serve as legal advisors to ensure the legal compliance in the project. The WP8 team has not been involved in preparation of the documents described in this deliverable (data sharing agreement, joint controller agreement, data protection impact assessment report, consent form and patient information leaflet) or ensuring compliance with the requirements of relevant regulations.

This work uses input from WP2 (clinical preparation), in particular the above-mentioned documents developed by UCD and other partners. This work may feed into WP1, WP2 and WP4; in particular the guidelines for clinical evaluation as well as the requirements of the AIA described in this report may be considered in these Work Packages.

2 Approach

This deliverable focuses on an analysis of the main EU regulations in the specific context of the CLASSICA system with the aim of understanding their relevance and impact on the work carried out in the CLASSICA project as well as the future commercialisation of the CLASSICA system. The analysis focuses on:

1. The General Data Protection Regulation [1] and the Medical Device Regulation [2], which are directly applicable laws in the EU. The AI Act [3], a new EU regulation which has been approved by the European Parliament in March 2024 and will enter into force in mid-2024, is also briefly addressed.
2. Relevant guidelines on implementing the GDPR and MDR issued by authoritative bodies, namely, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), Article 29 Working Party, and the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG). Unlike the regulations, these guidelines are not legally binding; however, any departure from the recommendations included in those documents should be well justified.
3. Documents developed within the CLASSICA project (mainly by UCD/MMUH in WP2) to meet the requirements of the GDPR and MDR. These include the data sharing agreement, joint controller agreement, data protection impact assessment (DPIA) report, patient information leaflet and consent form.
4. Relevant academic literature and reports issued by stakeholder groups.

To understand how partners have addressed the legal requirements for data protection and medical device software development, selected ethical concerns, and research quality issues (such as data quality), a questionnaire was developed and distributed (see Annex I). Additionally, the legal aspects of the project have been regularly discussed with partners at CLASSICA’s plenary meetings and monthly calls.

UCPH is the author of the deliverable. The deliverable has been reviewed by PSU, PT, and UCD. UCPH and PSU developed the questionnaire on legal issues. In addition, the teams at UCPH and PSU contributed to Task 8.1 through their publications on the topics covered by this task. The publications are cited in this deliverable.

3 Results

3.1 EU General Data Protection Regulation

The EU General Data Protection Regulation governs the processing of personal data in the EU. This chapter describes the key aspects of the GDPR relevant to the CLASSICA project with a focus on how they have been or will be addressed in the project. The issues discussed include:

- 1) an overview of the data processing activities in the CLASSICA project;
- 2) definitions of personal data, data concerning health, controller and processor;
- 3) legal grounds for data processing;
- 4) principles of data processing;
- 5) data controllers’ obligations.

Figure 1 below shows a “roadmap” of the GDPR, which may help readers navigate the topics discussed in this chapter.

Within Task 8.1, the WP8 team has also analysed the recent legal developments related to data transfers to third countries (that is, outside the European Economic Area). Data transfers to third countries are not planned within the CLASSICA project. However, since the topic of international data transfers is highlighted in the DoA under Task 8.1, this issue has been studied by the WP8 team. Based on the analyses, an article and book chapter have been published, which thoroughly discuss the recent legal developments with respect to data transfers to third countries, focusing on the USA [4, 5].

At the time of writing this report, the European Health Data Space regulation [6] is under development in the EU. This regulation will govern access to and control over health data, making it relevant to research projects like CLASSICA that use health data. However, it is uncertain whether the European Health Data Space will enter into force within the duration of the CLASSICA project. Due to this uncertainty and time constraints, this regulation is not addressed in the report.

The General Data Protection Regulation: Cheat Sheet

Figure 1. A roadmap illustrating the GDPR. This figure has been published in Mondschein and Monda (2019) [7] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

3.1.1 Data processing for scientific research purposes in the CLASSICA project

Patient data are collected and analysed in the CLASSICA project for the purpose of developing and evaluating the CLASSICA AI system. These activities are conducted within WP1, which focuses on the refinement and support of the CLASSICA system and WP4, which focuses on the clinical evaluation of the system. Patients' data used in these activities include:

- age;
- co-morbidities;
- medications;
- BMI (Body Mass Index);
- pre-operative biopsy results and radiological assessments;
- intra-operative recording: approx. 5 min. video of the inside of the patient's rectum including the tumour while a dye is being administered; and
- post-operative pathology evaluations and clinical course/outcome data.

The processing of these data is illustrated in Figure 2. The data are processed by four¹ clinical sites, which collect the data: MMUH (academic partner UCD), BBGRAZ, VUMC, ZOL and ARCTUR, a private company specialising in data analytics. ARCTUR is developing the CLASSICA tool under WP1. Each clinical site collects intra-operative video recordings and other clinical data, remove any identifying details and key-code the data by assigning an identifying number to each video recording and related clinical data. The sites retain encrypted keys that link these identifiers to patient names, stored on password-protected computers at each location.

The key-coded recordings and other clinical data are entered into an online data management platform, CLASSICA-OR run by ARCTUR. The UCD team has access to all the key-coded videos and clinical data through CLASSICA-OR to evaluate their quality. ARCTUR also has access to all the key-coded videos and clinical data and uses them to develop the CLASSICA system. The clinical sites are only able to access the data of their patients through CLASSICA-OR. The clinical sites have only access to the identifying key to the data of their patients and not the identifying keys to the data of patients from the other clinical sites. ARCTUR does not have access to the keys that link the identifying numbers to the patients' names.

¹ At the time of writing this report, UNITO, that is, the fifth clinical site involved in the project, has not yet obtained the ethical approval to conduct the first CLASSICA study and has not been processing data for the purpose of the CLASSICA project. ZOL has not started collecting the patients' data yet, however, it has obtained the ethical approval to conduct the first CLASSICA study. At the time of writing this report, additional clinical sites are being on-boarded for the first CLASSICA study. For description of the CLASSICA studies see Section 3.2.3.

Figure 2. Data processing in the CLASSICA project. This figure has been included in the DPIA report developed by UCD.

3.1.2 Definitions of personal data, data concerning health, controller and processor

Personal data and data concerning health

The GDPR defines personal data as

“any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person” Article 4(1)².

Patients’ data processed in the CLASSICA project (that is, age, co-morbidities, medications, body mass index, biopsy results and radiological assessments, intra-operative videos, post-operative pathology results and clinical course/outcome data) meet the definition of personal data as they are linked to patients’ names (at the moment of the collection) or can be relinked to patients’ names using the keys (see Section 3.1.1).

Importantly, the data processed within the CLASSICA project also satisfy the definition of “data concerning health” specified in Article 4(15) of the GDPR, namely “personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status”. Under the GDPR, data concerning health fall into a special category of data, which requires higher protection due to their sensitive nature as “the context of their processing could create significant risks to the fundamental rights and freedoms” (Recital 51).

² Unless specified otherwise, articles and recitals mentioned in this chapter refer to the GDPR.
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Anonymous data

Anonymous data are outside the scope of the GDPR. In line with Recital 26, anonymous data cannot identify the person directly or indirectly, taking into account “all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person”. It should be noted, however, that there are different approaches and guidelines on determining whether data are anonymous as well as a discussion on benefits and disadvantages of these various approaches [8, 9].

In the CLASSICA project, data collected by UCD via MMUH is considered anonymous in the hands of ARCTUR, pursuant to the data-sharing agreement between UCD and ARCTUR signed in September 2022 (Figure 3). The data sharing agreement specifies parties’ roles, responsibilities and rights with regards to the data sharing. According to the data sharing agreement between UCD and ARCTUR

“UCD will take all necessary steps to ensure that all personal data and information contained in Shared Information is anonymized and functionally separated, made illegible, de- identified or otherwise inaccessible whenever possible, such that it is no longer Personal Data, prior to providing the Shared Information to Arctur.”

The agreement also states that if ARCTUR came into contact with additional data “which would allow it to re-identify the data received from UCD [...], Arctur agrees to immediately destroy the Additional Data and inform UCD immediately of the manner of said destruction”. Hence, ARCTUR cannot relink the clinical data to the patients’ names without breaking the contract (the data sharing agreement) with UCD. It should be noted, however, that UCD has the key linking the data transferred to ARCTUR with the names of the patients. Consequently, one may question whether the dataset is anonymous in the hands of ARCTUR under the strict interpretation of the relevant provisions of the GDPR [9].

Figure 3. Data sharing agreement between UCD and ARCTUR.

Except for the above-mentioned dataset collected by MMUH (UCD) and transferred to ARCTUR, which is considered anonymous in the hands of ARCTUR pursuant to the data sharing agreement, the clinical data processed by ARCTUR, BBGRAZ, MMUH (UCD), VUMC and ZOL are personal and fall within the scope of the GDPR. ARCTUR processes, therefore, both anonymous data (according to the data sharing agreement between MMUH (UCD) and ARCTUR) received from MMUH (UCD) and personal data received from the other clinical sites, as described in the joint controller agreement (see below).

Data controller

Determining partners’ roles and responsibilities related to data processing in a multi-partner project involving data sharing among partners is a key issue. The GDPR distinguishes two types of entities that process data: controllers and processors.

- A controller “determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data” (Article 4(7)). If two or more controllers “jointly determine the purposes and means of processing” (Article 26) they act as joint controllers.
- A processor, in turn, “processes personal data on behalf of the controller” (Article 4(8)).

In the CLASSICA project, ARCTUR, BBGRAZ, UCD, VUMC and ZOL act as joint controllers and have signed the joint controller agreement pursuant to Article 26, which specifies the parties’ rights and obligations with regard to the processing activities, including data sharing (Figure 4). The agreement specifies that UCD and ARCTUR act as data receivers³, which means that they receive (personal) data from the data disclosers, that is the clinical sites (ZOL, VUMC and BBGRAZ).

None of the partners acts as a processor in the CLASSICA project.

Figure 4. Joint controller agreement between the UCD, ARCTUR, BBGRAZ, ZOL and VUMC.

3.1.3 Legal grounds for data processing in the CLASSICA project

The processing of personal data must be based on one of the **legal bases listed in Article 6(1)**. Additionally, the processing of a special category of personal data (such as data concerning health) is forbidden unless a **condition listed in Article 9(2)** is fulfilled (along with a legal basis for processing personal data included in Article 6(1)).

Selected legal bases (Article 6(1)) and conditions (Article 9(2)) relevant to research projects are summarised in Figure 5 below.

³ The GDPR does not use the terms “data receivers” and “data disclosers”. These terms are, however, used and defined in the joint controller agreement.

Figure 5. A summary of selected legal grounds for processing special categories of personal data. This figure has been published in de Kok et al. (2023) [10] under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

UCD relies on the following legal grounds for data processing: public interest or public task specified in Article 6(1)(e) in conjunction with fulfilling the condition for processing data concerning health outlined in Article 9(2)(j), namely the requirements for applying the so-called research exemption.

ARCTUR, BBGRAZ, VUMC and **ZOL** use consent specified in Article 6(1)(a) and the condition of explicit consent outlined in Article 9(2)(a) as the legal grounds for data processing.

Importantly, the clinical sites, which collect the data and share them with ARCTUR pursuant to the joint controller agreement (i.e., BBGRAZ, VUMC and ZOL; see Section 3.1.1 for details) are responsible for ensuring that ARCTUR has legitimate grounds for the processing under the GDPR as defined in the joint controller agreement. This means that patients' consent obtained by the clinical sites is used as the legal ground for data processing by both the clinical sites and ARCTUR.

Public interest/task and research exemption

Article 6(1)(e) states that data processing is lawful if it "is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller." UCD, through its research activities, fulfils a task in the public interest or exercises its official function

bestowed upon it by the state, which has a basis in Irish law, as described in the UCD’s DPIA report (see Section 3.1.5). The processing of the personal data is necessary for UCD to carry out these tasks.

According to Article 9(2)(j) the processing of data concerning health is not prohibited if it

“is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.”

All these conditions seem to be satisfied by the UCD.

First, the studies conducted within the **CLASSICA project satisfy the definition of scientific research** outlined in Article 29 Working Party “Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679 of 10 April 2018” [11]. According to that document, “scientific research” in the context of the GDPR “means a research project set up in accordance with relevant sector-related methodological and ethical standards, in conformity with good practice” [11].

Second, it is **necessary to use data concerning health** to achieve the scientific research purposes of the project, that is to develop and clinically validate the CLASSICA system. The purpose of the study cannot be achieved without processing data concerning health (this issue is addressed further below).

Third, UCD fulfils the requirements of Article 89(1), to which Article 9(2)(j) refers. Article 89(1) requires using **appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject** when data are processed for scientific research purposes. Article 89 (1) states that

“[t]hose safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes [i.e., archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes] can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.”

The data minimisation principle mentioned in Article 89(1) is defined in Article 5(1)(c), which states that personal data shall be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”. Hence, as put by Kindt et al. (2021) “[t]he aim of the safeguards, [...], is (i) to protect rights and freedoms of the data subjects and (ii) to process personal data as little as possible and only as needed to reach the objectives of the research” [12]. Kindt et al. (2021) also explain that

“discussion exists as to whether or not EEA [European Economic Area] States should adopt legislation imposing required safeguards for the processing of personal data for scientific research or if it is sufficient that controllers assess the feasibility to conduct the research respecting the data minimisation principle and providing for safeguards themselves” [12].

Indeed, Ireland, where UCD is based, has enacted legislation that mandates the implementation of the technical and organisational measures in the research context. These measures include, among other things, obtaining consent from data subjects. Consequently, UCD obtains consent from data subjects

to comply with Irish law. The section below focuses on the consent requirements as entrenched in Irish law.

Irish Health Research Regulations require obtaining consent from data subjects as a safeguard for the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject (Regulation 3(1)(e)) [13]. Specifically, a controller processing personal data for the purpose of health research must ensure that

“explicit consent has been obtained from the data subject, as a suitable and specific measure recorded and retained by the controller, and a copy of which is provided to the data subject prior to the commencement of the health research in accordance with international best practice on the ethical conduct of health research (which includes informed consent, transparency and independent ethical oversight) for the processing of his or her personal data for the purpose of specified health research, either in relation to a particular area or more generally in that area or a related area of health research, or part thereof” (Health Research Regulations, Regulation 3(1)(e)) [13].

The “Guidance on Explicit Consent Amendment to the Health Research Regulations January 2021” prepared by the Irish Department of Health in collaboration with other health and health research institutions, lists elements that characterise informed consent aligned with best practices. Such consent:

- “(i) identifies the scope of the specified research,
- (ii) provides information, in a timely manner, in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.
- (iii) gives choices to individuals in terms of the areas of research that they want their information to be used in and third parties that they are willing to have their information shared or not shared with,
- (iv) allows the withdrawal of consent in a convenient way and where that is not possible explains the limits of withdrawal,
- (v) is documented by the controller in written, electronic or other format with a copy of the record of consent provided to the individual” [14].

The consent form accompanied by the patient information leaflet used by UCD has met all these requirements. Both documents are attached to deliverable D2.1.

The above-mentioned Irish guidance document also stresses that “consent must always be voluntary without any element of inappropriate pressure or undue influence on the individual to participate”. The document also specifies that researchers must ensure that research participants are

“expressly advised that the giving or not giving of consent for the processing of his or her personal data for research or its withdrawal will not be the cause of any adverse or reduced care and treatment by a health practitioner providing care and treatment to the data subject” [14].

These requirements have been addressed in consent forms used by UCD. The forms include the following section:

“5.2.1.3 Do I have to take part? Can I withdraw?”

No, you do not have to take part. Participation in any study, including this one, is voluntary. If you do decide to take part, you may withdraw your consent to take part at any time without giving us a reason. Your doctor will not be upset if you decide not to take part. Your treatment and care will not be affected if you decide not to participate in this study.”

Consent

Consent is used as the legal ground for data processing by ARCTUR, BBGRAZ, VUMC and ZOL.

Consent is defined in the GDPR as

“any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her” Article 4(11).

The requirements for consent of an adult person to the processing of data concerning health are also included in Article 6(1)(a), 7, 9(2)(a) and Recitals 32, 42 and 43. In summary, valid consent for processing data concerning health should be freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous, and explicit. The data subjects must also be able to withdraw the consent (Article 7(3)).

According to Recital 42, consent can be considered as **freely given** when the data subject has freedom to make a choice about participation in research and will not face negative consequences in case of the refusal to participate. Recital 43 indicates that the use of consent as the legal basis for data processing when the data controller is a public authority (as defined by the national law) may be problematic. Recital 43 explains that

“[i]n order to ensure that consent is freely given, consent should not provide a valid legal ground for the processing of personal data in a specific case where there is a clear imbalance between the data subject and the controller, in particular where the controller is a public authority and it is therefore unlikely that consent was freely given in all the circumstances of that specific situation”.

However, as explained by the EDBP, “the use of consent as a lawful basis for data processing by public authorities is not totally excluded under the legal framework of the GDPR” [15].

In the context of the CLASSICA project and the use of consent as the legal basis, clinical sites must ensure that the provision of healthcare is not contingent on patients agreeing to the processing of their data for research purposes.

Specific consent means consent given “to the processing of [...] personal data for one or more specific purposes” (Article 6(a)). Consent forms used in the CLASSICA project should, therefore, specify that patients’ data are used for the purpose of research within the CLASSICA project, which aims to develop and evaluate an AI-based support system for tumour surgery.

Informed consent entails providing patients with elements of information specified in Articles 13 and 14 prior to obtaining their consent. These elements of information include purposes of and legal basis for the processing, the identity and contact details of the controller, and information about the data recipients (i.e., entities to which the data are disclosed, Article 4(9)), if relevant, among other things. Data subjects must also be informed about the right to withdraw the consent (Article 7(3)).

Importantly, clinical sites that share the data with ARCTUR (pursuant to the joint controller agreement) must inform the patients that their data will be processed by ARCTUR, which acts as a joint controller.

If this condition is not fulfilled, the consent obtained by the clinical sites cannot be used as valid legal basis for ARCTUR's data processing.

Unambiguous consent means unequivocal acceptance of the proposed data processing (see Recital 32). To ensure that consent from the patients is unambiguous, written consent, which clearly defines data processing activities, should be obtained. By collecting signatures on consent forms, the partners also ensure the compliance with Article 7(1), which states that the controller must be able to prove that the data subject consented to data processing.

Consent must also be **explicit** to fulfil the condition for processing a special category of data (e.g., data concerning health) outlined in Article 9(2)(a). Bygrave and Tosoni explain that in this context

“‘explicit’ means that the process of requesting and providing consent must occur as a formally separate process to the other transaction(s) to which the consent attaches, and that process must involve a specific request by the controller for permission from the data subject to process the data in question, followed by a specific reply in the affirmative” [16].

The condition for explicit consent seems to be related to a requirement included in Article 7(2):

“[i]f the data subject's consent is given in the context of a written declaration which also concerns other matters, the request for consent shall be presented in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from the other matters, in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.”

This requirement may be met by including a separate section dedicated to data processing, which contains a statement of consent specifically to processing data concerning health for clearly defined research purpose, to which the patients may agree by ticking a box.

Article 7(3) states that data subjects have the **right to withdraw consent** at any time. However, it also specifies that

“[t]he withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal. Prior to giving consent, the data subject shall be informed thereof. It shall be as easy to withdraw as to give consent.”

3.1.4 Principles of data processing

Article 5 sets out principles that a data controller must comply with. These include lawfulness, fairness, and transparency (Article 5(1)(a)); purpose limitation (Article 5(1)(b)); data minimisation (Article 5(1)(c)); accuracy (Article 5(1)(d)); storage limitation (Article 5(1)(e)); integrity and confidentiality (Article 5(1)(f)); and accountability (Article 5(2)). The following paragraphs describe examples of how these principles have been addressed in the CLASSICA project.

Lawfulness

The lawfulness of data processing involves relying on adequate legal grounds for the processing, which are addressed in Section 3.1.3.

Fairness

The EDPB explains that fairness “is an overarching principle which requires that personal data should not be processed in a way that is unjustifiably detrimental, unlawfully discriminatory, unexpected or

misleading to the data subject” [17]. In another guidance document, the EDPB states that fairness “includes, inter alia, recognising the reasonable expectations of the data subjects, considering possible adverse consequences processing may have on them, and having regard to the relationship and potential effects of imbalance between them and the controller” [18]. Reasonable expectations of the data subjects may be particularly relevant when considering additional studies (“secondary research”) [19] involving the data initially collected specifically for the purpose of the CLASSICA studies. The CLASSICA consortium does not envision such secondary research at this moment, and only anonymised data will be made available outside the CLASSICA project. Potential adverse consequences of data processing mentioned by the EDPB, such as risks of malicious hacking have been addressed within the DPIA (see Section 3.1.5).

Transparency

The EDPB explains that transparency “is about enabling data subjects to understand, and if necessary, make use of their rights in Articles 15 to 22. The principle is embedded in Articles 12, 13, 14 and 34” [17]. Article 12 focuses on the transparency and communication of the elements of information outlined in Articles 13 and 14 as well as communication related to the data subjects’ rights addressed in subsequent articles and facilitating the exercise of these rights. It specifies that the controller must communicate the information “in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language” (Article 12). Articles 13 and 14, meanwhile, list the elements of information that must be communicated to the data subjects in order to respect their **right to be informed**. These include information about purposes of and legal basis for the processing, contact details of the controller, and information that the data will be processed by the data recipients (if this is the case), among other things. Patient information leaflets distributed by MMUH (UCD) to the data subjects, along with consent forms, include clear and accessible information about the data processing, including the purpose of the processing, data subjects’ rights, and legal bases for the processing.

As touched upon earlier, the data subjects’ rights are addressed in Articles 15 to 22. Article 15 describes the **right to access**, stating that “[t]he data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller confirmation as to whether or not personal data concerning him or her are being processed, and, where that is the case, access to the personal data” as well as information about, among other things, the purposes of the processing, categories of data processed, and period of their storage. Subsequent Articles 16 and 17 establish the **right to rectification** of inaccurate personal data (including the completion of incomplete data) and the **right to erasure** of personal data in certain cases, for example, when a data subject withdraws the consent, and there is no other legal ground for data processing (Article 17(1)(b)). Data subjects also have the **right to restriction of processing** in certain cases (Article 18), for example, when “the accuracy of the personal data is contested by the data subject, for a period enabling the controller to verify the accuracy of the personal data” (Article 18(1)(a)). **Right to data portability** means that a data subject is entitled

“to receive the personal data concerning him or her, which he or she has provided to a controller, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and [has] the right to transmit those data to another controller without hindrance from the controller to which the personal data have been provided” (Article 20(1)).

A data subject may also **object the processing** “on grounds relating to his or her particular situation, at any time to processing of personal data concerning him or her” when the processing is based on the

public interest (Article 6(1)(e)) or legitimate interests (Article 6(1)(f)) (Article 21(1)). The right to object cannot, however, be exercised when data are processed for scientific research and at the same time “the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest” (Article 21(6)). The exception does not apply, however, when the legal basis is a public task carried out to exercise the official authority vested in the controller (see the distinction in Article 6(1)(e)). The GDPR also establishes the right “not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing” (Article 22).

Importantly, Article 89(2) states that

“[w]here personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes”.

In line with this provision, Ireland has established the following derogations for scientific research:

“[...] where processing of data is for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, the rights of a data subject set out in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 are restricted to the extent that—

(a) the exercise of any of those rights would be likely to render impossible, or seriously impair, the achievement of those purposes, and

(b) such restriction is necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.” (Section 61(2) of Data Protection Act 2018 [20]).

The Member States, in which the other CLASSICA partners are based may have enacted similar laws; analysis of these laws is beyond the scope of this deliverable.

To respect the principle of transparency, UCD informs the data subjects about the limits to their rights in the patient information leaflet:

“Your rights to access, change or move your information are limited as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate.”

Purpose limitation

The purpose limitation principle entails that data are “collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes” (Article 5(1)(b)). The purpose of data processing in the CLASSICA project has been defined in line with this principle and described, for example, in the joint controller agreement as facilitation of “scientific research in the public interest, namely the CLASSICA Study”.

Article 5(1)(b) also addresses the potential **secondary uses of the data for research purposes**, creating an exemption to the purpose limitation for research. It states that “further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes”.

Article 89(1) is described in section 3.1.3. In addition, the guidance of the EDPB in the context of secondary research with data concerning health and Article 89(1) highlights that

“considering the sensitive nature of health data and the risks when re-using health data for the purpose of scientific research, strong measures must be taken in order to ensure an appropriate level of security as required by Article 32 (1) GDPR” [21].

Article 32 is addressed in Section 3.1.5.

As previously described, secondary research using the CLASSICA data is not envisioned. However, there is a plan to anonymise the data collected within CLASSICA and make them available for further research in abridged form through various repositories, in line with FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles. These data will not fall into the scope of the GDPR. The details on data sharing for further research are included in deliverables D2.4 and D2.5 (data management plan).

Data minimisation

This principle requires data to be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed” (Article 5(1)(c)).

To address this principle, controllers should consider the following questions:

- Is processing personal data necessary to achieve a given purpose?
- Is it possible to process less (detailed) personal data to achieve the purpose?

These aspects should be considered both before data processing and during the processing activities [17].

The EDPB explains that in the research context data minimisation can be addressed by specifying the research questions “and assessing the type and amount of data necessary to properly answer these research questions” [21]. This requirement has been met in the CLASSICA project as the research questions have been clearly defined in the DoA as follows:

- “Can other surgeons use the system and get similar results from their specific patient cohorts?”
- “Can the system enable optimal choice of biopsied tissue, and thus reduce biopsy error?”
- “Can the system increase the completeness and accuracy of tumour resection?”

The type and amount of the data used in CLASSICA were determined in such a way to be able to answer these questions.

Pseudonymisation is one of the measures implemented in the CLASSICA project to respect the principle of data minimisation.

The GDPR defines pseudonymisation as

“the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person” (Article 4(5)).

In the CLASSICA project, clinicians who collect the data at the clinical sites ensure that the data are pseudonymised. They remove any identifying details from the videos and assign each video and clinical data an identifying number which links the data to the patient. Pseudonymisation keys that link the identifying numbers to the names of the patients are stored encrypted at each clinical site on password-protected computers.

Anonymisation of the data through the destruction of the pseudonymisation keys was considered for the CLASSICA project. Anonymisation would make reidentifying the data subjects impossible and hence render the data outside of the scope of the GDPR once anonymised. However, that solution would negatively affect the usefulness of the data for this research project and consequently could make it impossible to achieve the scientific research purpose of the CLASSICA project. As long as the data are key-coded, it is possible to reidentify individual patients to study them further. This possibility may be used when it is necessary to gain more information about the patients, that is, when a patient's video analysis generates a result that appears to be an outlier. Information about the patients whose results appear as outliers could help refine the exclusion criteria in future uses of the CLASSICA system.

Another measure implemented in the CLASSICA project to respect the principle of data minimisation is limiting access to personal data. Each clinical site can access only the data of their own patients, and not the data from patients recruited at other sites.

Accuracy

The principle of accuracy requires ensuring that personal data are

“accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay” (Article 5(d)).

This principle has been addressed in the CLASSICA project by the implementation of a data quality assuring step. The UCD team assesses the intraoperative videos uploaded to the CLASSICA-OR platform to ensure that only high-quality data are used to train the CLASSICA system.

Storage limitation

The storage limitation principle requires the data to be “kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed” (Article 5(1)(e)). Storage of data for scientific research purposes is, however, one of the exceptions from this limitation. In that case, personal data may be stored for a longer time provided that the processing is “in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject” (Article 5(1)(e)).

Integrity and confidentiality

The principles of integrity and confidentiality entail that data are “processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures” (Article 5(2)(f)).

When commenting on these principles applied in the context of scientific research on health data, the EDPB highlights that such “health data merit higher protection as their processing is likelier to lead to negative impacts for data subjects” [21]. Consequently, “appropriate technical and organisational up-to-date measures must be implemented to ensure a sufficient level of security” [21]. The EDPB provides a minimum list of such measures, which include: pseudonymisation, encryption, non-disclosure agreements and strict access role distribution, access role restrictions, and access logs [21]. Technical and organisational measures implemented in CLASSICA to ensure data security are described below, in section 3.1.5.

In the context of the principles of integrity and confidentiality, the EDPB also highlights the necessity to conduct a DPIA if certain conditions are met [21]. DPIA addressing data processing in the CLASSICA project is described in Section 3.1.5.

Other issues mentioned by the EDPB in relation to integrity and confidentiality include the significance of data protection officers and documentation of the measures used to protect data [21]. These issues are addressed in Section 3.1.5.

Accountability

Accountability requires controllers to “be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with” the above-mentioned principles (Article 5(2)). Corrales Compagnucci et al. (2023) explain (in the context of the DPIA, see section 3.1.5) that

“[i]n practical terms, this entails that controllers are obligated to maintain detailed documentation that validates their compliance. The DPIA is a key accountability mechanism in itself, but it should further specify other means of ensuring [that] compliance can be demonstrated, such as specifying a systematic record of data processing activities. This should capture information about data categories, the purposes of processing, and details of data recipients, among other things. The activities of an organisation’s DPO [data protection officer], which is required for entities involved in inter alia large-scale of processing sensitive data as most healthcare research does, provides a further means of demonstrating accountability” [19].

The DPIA report addressing data processing within CLASSICA along with information about the data protection officer are described in section 3.1.5.

3.1.5 Data controllers’ obligations

Data protection by design and by default

The GDPR imposes certain obligations on data controllers. In broad terms a “controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with this Regulation” (Article 24). Subsequent articles, especially Article 25 and 32 specify the obligations entailed by this provision. Article 25, entitled “**Data protection by design and by default**”, states that

“the controller shall [...] implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, which are designed to implement data-protection principles, such as data minimisation, in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the

processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation and protect the rights of data subjects.”

The measures should be implemented taking into account “the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons” (Article 25). As explained by the EDPB the

“[t]echnical and organizational measures and necessary safeguards can be understood in a broad sense as any method or means that a controller may employ in the processing. Being appropriate means that the measures and necessary safeguards should be suited to achieve the intended purpose, i.e. they must implement the data protection principles effectively. The requirement to appropriateness is thus closely related to the requirement of effectiveness. A technical or organisational measure and safeguard can be anything from the use of advanced technical solutions to the basic training of personnel.” [17]

The measures implemented in the CLASSICA are described in Section 3.1.4 above.

Security measures

Article 32 focuses specifically on the measures to ensure security. It states that

“the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, including inter alia as appropriate:

- (a) the pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data,
- (b) the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services;
- (c) the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;
- (d) a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.”

Similarly to Article 25, Article 32 states that the measures should be implemented taking into account “the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons”. Furthermore, point 2 of Article 32 stresses the importance of considering the risks related to the processing when evaluating the adequate level of security. These risks may be related to “accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed” (Article 32(2)).

Pseudonymisation has been implemented in the CLASSICA project and is described in Section 3.1.4.

Encryption is also used in the project, in particular, for data sharing between the clinical sites and data receivers (Figure 4), as described in the joint controller agreement as well as for data sharing between MMUH (UCD) and ARCTUR (Figure 3).

To ensure confidentiality, **system access authorisation privileges** have been implemented. Each clinical site has access to the data of their patients but not the data of patients recruited at other clinical sites.

At UCD specifically, as described in the DPIA report, **access logs** of all devices on which project data may be stored and consulted will be kept. All members of the UCD research team also hold a certificate of completed **GDPR training** and “Information Security Awareness for Staff and Researchers”. Moreover, UCD has implemented policies such as the UCD Research Data Management Policy [22] and IT policies. As per the joint controller agreement, UCD and ARCTUR also “have committed themselves to confidentiality or are under an appropriate statutory obligation of confidentiality”.

The security measures implemented by ARCTUR are described in the DPIA report prepared by the UCD as follows:

“Arctur is ISO 9001 (quality management systems) and 27001 (information security management) certified. The Arctur data centre is located on its own premises and all physical access is restricted to a limited number of staff with appropriate training who have been granted access in line with their professional duties. The servers are managed according to the best practices and standards, meaning, e.g., remote access to the servers is restricted to Arctur staff with appropriate training. The operating system and installed applications are kept updated with latest security patches via the automatic configuration management system. The Arctur Security Team runs both host and network-based intrusion detection systems. It monitors the traffic flow, pattern and contents into and out of Arctur networks in order to detect attacks. All data captured will be securely transmitted and stored on the high-security data platform at Arctur, and all access to Arctur domains happens over HTTPS with the highest encryption level supported by the browser. Business continuity and data availability are guaranteed by Arctur, with an agreed Recovery Time Objective (RTO) and a Recovery Point Objective.”

Records of processing activities

Another obligation of the controller is to keep a record of the processing activities. Details that should be recorded are outlined in Article 30(1) and include, among other things, “a description of the categories of data subjects and of the categories of personal data”, the purposes of the processing, and, where possible, a description of the security measures required by Article 32. In accordance with the joint controller agreement, each partner who signed it is responsible for compliance with this requirement for their respective site. The records must be made available to the supervisory authority if requested (Article 30(4)).

Data protection officer

Under certain conditions, controllers are required to designate a data protection officer. These conditions are fulfilled by the CLASSICA partners who process the data, as they are either public bodies (Article 37(1)(a)) or their “core activities” consist of “processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9” (Article 37(1)(b)). Names and contact details of data protection officers designated by the partners are listed in the joint controller agreement. Importantly, a data protection officer should enjoy certain independence from the data controller and “[t]he controller [...] shall ensure that the data protection officer does not receive any instructions regarding the exercise of [his]

tasks” (Article 38(3)). Data protection officers may also be contacted by the data subjects regarding the processing of their data and their rights under the GDPR (Article 38(4)). The tasks of the data protection officer include, among other things, informing and advising the controllers about their obligations under the GDPR, monitoring compliance with the GDPR, and giving advice when needed about the DPIA (Article 39(1)).

Another obligation of the data controllers is to notify of a **personal data breach** the supervisory authority pursuant to Article 33, and if applicable, communicate the data breach to the data subjects (Article 34).

Data protection impact assessment

As discussed previously, in certain cases, the controllers are also required to conduct a DPIA prior to the processing. DPIA is “an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data” (Article 35(1)). Such an assessment is required when

“processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons” (Article 35(1)).

The GDPR outlines types of processing that may entail such risks, such as large-scale processing of special categories of data. Corrales Compagnucci et al. (2023) conclude their analysis of the types of processing that qualify for the DPIA by stating that

“[c]onsidering the sensitive nature of the data involved and the potential inclusion of vulnerable data subjects it becomes evident that a default assumption should be established: data sharing projects in the health sciences that involve personal data will most likely require a DPIA” [19].

Consequently, it seems that the CLASSICA partners which process the personal data should conduct the DPIA.

The DPIA report prepared by UCD addresses all the elements required by the GDPR, that is, 1) a systematic description of the planned data processing activities and their purposes; 2) an examination of the necessity and proportionality of the processing with respect to the purposes; 3) an evaluation of the risks to data subjects’, and 4) description how the risks will be addressed “including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with this Regulation taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned” (Article 35 (7)).

3.2 EU Medical Device Regulation

In order to place the CLASSICA software on the EU market, the manufacturer (i.e., the entity that develops and then markets the device under its name) must comply with the Medical Device Regulation. This chapter focuses on the selected key aspects of the MDR that are relevant to the CLASSICA project. These include:

- 1) early-stage considerations;
- 2) general safety and performance requirements;
- 3) requirements for clinical evaluation; and
- 4) conformity assessment.

US legal framework for medical AI devices is discussed in an article of the WP8 team [23].

3.2.1 *Early-stage considerations*

Definition of medical devices and determination of the intended use

The MDR defines the term “medical device” as:

“any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes:

- diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease,
- diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability,
- investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state,
- providing information by means of *in vitro* examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood and tissue donations, and which does not achieve its principal intended action by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means, in or on the human body, but which may be assisted in its function by such means” Article 2(1)⁴.

Defining the intended use of the device is, therefore, key to determining whether a device falls into the scope of the MDR. Beckers et al. (2021) explain that:

“[d]efining the intended use of a future device is the starting point for all following decisions, including whether or not it qualifies as a medical device. The intended use covers two aspects: (1) the actual medical purpose, e.g., which disease or injury can be diagnosed, treated, or monitored, and (2) the authorised use, understood as defining the intended users and use environment, target patient population, or body parts. Properly described, the intended purpose will therefore provide: (a) confirmation of, whether the regulation applies, (b) the basis for the classification of the future device into one of four risk classes, as required by

⁴Unless specified otherwise, articles and recitals mentioned in this chapter refer to the MDR.

Article 51 and (c), the starting point for downstream development activities, clinical evaluation and product documentation” [24].

The intended use of the CLASSICA system has been generally defined at the start of the project and may be refined further during the project. The intended patient populations are patients with rectal tumours, while the intended users are cancer surgeons. The purpose of the CLASSICA system is to aid the diagnosis and treatment of rectal tumours, which entails that the CLASSICA system falls into the scope of the MDR.

As explained by the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG), medical device software “can be placed on the market in two different ways: as a medical device [...] in its own right or as an integral component or part of a hardware device” [25]. In the latter case, the hardware-software combination would be assessed as a whole in the regulatory process. The CLASSICA partners envision that the CLASSICA system will be placed on the market as medical device software in its own right.

Risk classification

The MDR provides a risk classification rule specifically for medical device software. Rule 11 states that:

“[s]oftware intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa, except if such decisions have an impact that may cause:

- death or an irreversible deterioration of a person's state of health, in which case it is in class III; or
- a serious deterioration of a person's state of health or a surgical intervention, in which case it is classified as class IIb.

Software intended to monitor physiological processes is classified as class IIa, except if it is intended for monitoring of vital physiological parameters, where the nature of variations of those parameters is such that it could result in immediate danger to the patient, in which case it is classified as class IIb.

All other software is classified as class I” (MDR Annex VIII, section 6.3, Rule 11).

Figure 6 depicts the risk classes in the context of the level of the risk.

Figure 6. Risk classes in the MDR. This figure has been published in Cepeda Zapata et al. 2023 [26] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

UCD and ARCTUR determined that the CLASSICA system qualifies as class IIa medical device software.

Future modifications to medical device software

When planning the evaluation and future development of the software one must keep in mind that a continuous-learning software, that is software which learns and in real time updates its performance during the clinical use, in principle cannot be currently placed on the market in the EU under the MDR. This may, however, change under the AI Act as discussed in Section 3.3.4.

With regard to the approach of the MDR to software modifications, as explained by Prinz et al. (2023)

“[a]ccording to Annex I, Chapter II, Section 17.1 MDR, software must be designed to ensure repeatability, reliability and performance in accordance with its intended use. The CE conformity assessment and subsequent placing on the market is therefore usually coupled with a defined technical development status. In the further life cycle, however, medical devices are usually subject to technical changes which, depending on their scope and criticality, may also require a renewed CE conformity assessment.” [27]

Changes to medical devices are addressed, among others, in Article 10(9), which states that

“[c]hanges in device design or characteristics [...] shall be adequately taken into account in a timely manner.”

More specifically, as detailed in the subsequent paragraph of Article 10(9), “a strategy for regulatory compliance, including compliance with conformity assessment procedures and procedures for management of modifications to the devices” should be addressed in the quality management system.

Specific procedures for introducing substantial changes to medical devices, for example, changes affecting the performance and safety of the device, depending on the type of conformity procedure (see Section 3.2.5), which was used to evaluate the compliance with the MDR are outlined in Annex IX, Chapter II, section 4.10 and Annex X, section 5.2.

3.2.2 General safety and performance requirements

To place a device on the market, the manufacturer must meet the applicable general safety and performance requirements outlined in Annex I. These include:

- general requirements, which include achieving the intended performance, safety and effectiveness and establishment of a risk management system, among other things (Chapter 1 of Annex I);
- requirements regarding design and manufacture (Chapter 2 of Annex I), which concern, for example, the usability of the device;
- requirements regarding the information supplied with the device (Chapter 3 of Annex I).

Harmonised standards

To demonstrate conformity with the general safety and performance requirements, the manufacturers may implement harmonised standards. Harmonised standards include solutions and technical details that support the general safety and performance requirements included in the MDR. A full list of standards that have already been deemed to satisfy the respective requirements of the MDR is available on the website of the European Commission [28]. The use of the standards is voluntary; however, as stated in Article 8 of the MDR “[d]evices that are in conformity with the relevant

harmonised standards, or the relevant parts of those standards [...] shall be presumed to be in conformity with the requirements of this Regulation covered by those standards or parts thereof.”

As reported by ARCTUR in the questionnaire on legal issues, the CLASSICA system is or will be manufactured, controlled and tested in accordance with the following standards:

- EN 20417:2021 Information supplied by the manufacturer of medical devices,
- EN ISO 13485:2016+A11:2021 Medical devices – Quality management systems - Requirements for regulatory purposes,
- EN ISO 14971:2019+A11:2021 Medical devices – Application of risk management to medical devices,
- EN ISO 15223-1:2021 Medical devices – Symbols to be used with medical device labels, labelling and information to be supplied – Part 1: General requirements,
- EN ISO 14155:2020 Clinical investigation of medical devices for human subjects - Good clinical practice,
- EN ISO 62304:2006+A1:2015 Medical device software – Software life cycle processes, and
- EN ISO 62366-1:2015 Medical devices – Application of usability engineering to medical devices.

3.2.3 Clinical evaluation

Manufacturers must conduct the clinical evaluation of a medical device software to confirm the compliance with the general safety and performance requirements (Article 61), such as the ability of the device to achieve its intended performance and its safety (Annex I).

The clinical evaluation under the MDR involves:

- “(1) preparation (and updating) of a clinical evaluation plan;
- (2) identification of relevant clinical data (both generated by the manufacturer and available in scientific literature) and of gaps in the available evidence through a systematic literature review;
- (3) appraisal of the available data, including the methodological quality and scientific validity, as well as their relevance to the clinical evaluation of the device;
- (4) clinical investigation (involving human subjects), which is mandatory for class III and implantable devices, but necessary for other devices only if it is needed to address gaps in the evidence;
- (5) analysis of all relevant clinical data to evaluate whether they demonstrate conformity with the general safety and performance requirements (Annex XIV of the MDR).” [29]

In the case of the CLASSICA system, the key clinical data will be generated in the CLASSICA project. In particular, three studies will be conducted within WP4:

- Study 1: generalisability and usability validation study, which aims to validate the results of a previous study conducted by UCD, at different clinical sites;
- Study 2: biopsy validation, which aims to assess the use of the CLASSICA system for guiding endoscopic biopsy; and
- Study 3: resection validation study aiming to evaluate the use the CLASSICA system for the assessment of tumour margins during Transanal Minimally Invasive Surgery.

The studies are described in more detail in the DoA and deliverable D2.1. UCD has consulted the Irish Health Products Regulatory Authority on the status of the studies, as described in deliverable D2.3. The agency has clarified that Study 2 and 3 qualify as clinical investigations under the MDR, that is “systematic investigation[s] involving one or more human subjects, undertaken to assess the safety or performance of a device” (Article 2(45)). Study 1 is not considered to involve human subjects, in line with MDCG guidelines [30], as the analyses conducted within that study do not impact patient management and do not introduce additional risks. Therefore, Study 1 does not qualify as clinical investigation. The requirements for the clinical investigation are discussed below. Importantly, none of the CLASSICA studies involves testing medicinal products and, therefore, none of them is subject to the EU Clinical Trials Regulation (536/2014).

Clinical investigation

Clinical investigation is specifically addressed in Articles 62-82, which include some good clinical practice requirements.

As specified in Article 62(1), clinical investigation can be conducted for one or more of the following purposes:

- “(a) to establish and verify that, under normal conditions of use, a device is designed, manufactured and packaged in such a way that it is suitable for one or more of the specific purposes listed in point (1) of Article 2, and achieves the performance intended as specified by its manufacturer;
- (b) to establish and verify the clinical benefits of a device as specified by its manufacturer;
- (c) to establish and verify the clinical safety of the device and to determine any undesirable side-effects, under normal conditions of use of the device, and assess whether they constitute acceptable risks when weighed against the benefits to be achieved by the device.”

An overarching requirement for the clinical investigations is articulated in Article 62(3), which states that

“[c]linical investigations shall be designed and conducted in such a way that the rights, safety, dignity and well-being of the subjects participating in a clinical investigation are protected and prevail over all other interests and the clinical data generated are scientifically valid, reliable and robust.”

The subsequent points and articles include more specific requirements, such as, for:

- an authorisation from the Member State, in which the clinical investigation will take place (Article 62(4)(a), Article 70, and Annex XV Chapter II);
- ethical review of the study by an ethical committee (Article 62(3)); the opinion of the ethics committee must not be negative (Article 62(4)(b));
- acceptable benefit-risk ratio, which indicates that “the anticipated benefits to the subjects or to public health justify the foreseeable risks and inconveniences” (Article 62(4)(e));
- informed consent of research subjects - detailed requirements for informed consent are outlined in Article 63 and include, among other things, a requirement for “a prior interview with a member of the investigating team who is appropriately qualified under national law”, requirement to ensure that data subject has enough time to make the decision about

the participation in the study and the elements of information that must be provided to the research subjects;

- safeguarding research subjects’ rights to physical and mental integrity, privacy, and data protection (Article 62(4)(h));
- harm (i.e., pain, discomfort and fear) minimization and risk minimization (Article 62(4)(i));
- provision of medical care by qualified personnel under clinical investigation conditions (Article 62(4)(j));
- lack of undue influence on the research subjects to participate in the study (Article 62(4)(k));
- the device’s compliance with the general safety and performance requirements except those covered by the clinical investigation (Article 62(4)(l)). This means that a risk management system and preclinical evaluation should be implemented/completed before the start of the clinical investigation.

Annex XV includes further requirements for clinical investigations, including the ethical principles that should be followed, methodology, and documents needed to apply for clinical investigation (e.g., application form, investigator’s brochure, clinical investigation plan, technical documentation, patient information sheet and informed consent document), and obligations of the sponsor that have not been listed earlier in the text of the MDR (e.g., to prepare a clinical investigation report and to appoint a monitor).

At the time of writing this report, the documents needed to apply for the clinical investigation are being compiled in the CLASSICA project. UCD will submit the documents to the National Research Ethics Committee for Clinical Investigations of Medical Devices and Performance Studies of *In Vitro* Diagnostic Medical Devices (NREC-MD), which is an Irish institution that authorises clinical investigations under the MDR. The details of this process are described in deliverable D2.3. The other clinical sites must submit the documents to their corresponding national authorities. The clinical sites will follow the harmonised standard EN ISO 14155:2020 “Clinical investigation of medical devices for human subjects - Good clinical practice” to meet the requirements of the MDR on clinical investigation.

Guidelines on clinical evaluation

The following guidance documents issued under MDR are relevant to the CLASSICA’s clinical evaluation:

- Guidance on clinical evaluation (MDR) / Performance evaluation (IVDR) of medical device software [MDCG 2020-1](#);
- Guidance on safety reporting in clinical investigations [MDCG 2020-10/1 Rev.1](#);
- Regulation (EU) 2017/745 – Questions & Answers regarding clinical investigation 1 [MDCG 2021-6 - Rev.1](#);
- Clinical investigation application/notification documents MDCG 2021-8 [MDCG 2021-8](#);
- Commission Guidance on the content and structure of the summary of the clinical investigation report [2023/C 163/06](#);
- Guidance on content of the Clinical Investigation Plan for clinical investigations of medical devices [MDCG 2024-3](#);
- Guidance on the Investigator’s Brochure content [MDCG 2024-5](#).

All the guidance documents issued under the MDR are available on the European Commission website: https://health.ec.europa.eu/medical-devices-sector/new-regulations/guidance-mdcg-endorsed-documents-and-other-guidance_en#sec4.

Table 1 summarizes three aspects, which should be addressed in the clinical evaluation of medical device software as specified in the MDCG document MDCG 2020-1.

Table 1. A summary of the aspects of the clinical evaluation of medical device software outlined in the MDCG guidance document MDCG 2020-1 [31].

Clinical association	Technical Performance	Clinical Performance
<p>"the association of [a medical device software] output with a clinical condition or physiological state" [31]</p> <p style="text-align: center;">output ↓ clinical condition/ physiological state</p>	<p>"capability [...] to accurately and reliably generate the intended technical [...] output from the input data" [31]</p> <p style="text-align: center;">input ↓ software ↓ output</p>	<p>the ability to achieve the intended purpose, "thereby leading to a clinical benefit for patients" [31]</p> <p style="text-align: center;">input ↓ software ↓ intended purpose (incl. clinical benefit)</p>

There are also guidelines for studies evaluating medical AI systems developed by various professional groups (Table 2). These documents may help the CLASSICA partners to design and conduct studies of high methodological quality and scientific validity and, in this way, meet the requirements for the clinical evaluation of the MDR.

Table 2. A list of selected guidelines on evaluation of medical AI systems.

Acronym	Full name	Publication
CONSORT-AI	Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials	Liu X, Cruz Rivera S, Moher D, et al. Reporting guidelines for clinical trial reports for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the CONSORT-AI. <i>Nat Med</i> 26, 1364–1374 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-1034-x
DECIDE-AI	Developmental and Exploratory Clinical Investigation of DEcision-support systems driven by Artificial Intelligence	Vasey, B., et al. "DECIDE-AI: a new reporting guideline and its relevance to artificial intelligence studies in radiology." <i>Clinical Radiology</i> 78.2 (2023): 130-136.
MI-CLAIM	Minimum information about clinical artificial intelligence modeling	Norgeot B, Quer G, Beaulieu-Jones BK, et al. Minimum information about clinical artificial intelligence modeling: the MI-CLAIM checklist. <i>Nat Med</i> . 2020;26(9):1320-1324. doi:10.1038/s41591-020-1041-y

Acronym	Full name	Publication
MINIMAR	MINimum Information for Medical AI Reporting	Hernandez-Boussard T, Bozkurt S, Ioannidis JPA, Shah NH. MINIMAR (MINimum Information for Medical AI Reporting): Developing reporting standards for artificial intelligence in health care. J Am Med Inform Assoc. 2020 Dec 9;27(12):2011-2015. doi: 10.1093/jamia/ocaa088
SPIRIT-AI	Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials–Artificial Intelligence	Cruz Rivera S, Liu X, Chan A-W, et al. Guidelines for clinical trial protocols for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the SPIRIT-AI extension. Nat Med 2020;26:1351–63.
TREE-AI	Transparency, Replicability, Ethics and Effectiveness.	Vollmer S, Mateen BA, Bohner G, et al. Machine learning and AI research for patient benefit: 20 critical questions on transparency, replicability, ethics and effectiveness. 2018.
-	Guidelines for developing and reporting machine learning predictive models in biomedical research: a multidisciplinary view.	Luo W, Phung D, Tran T, et al. Guidelines for developing and reporting machine learning predictive models in biomedical research: a multidisciplinary view. J Med Internet Res 2016; 18: e323.

The use of the guidelines in the CLASSICA project has been described by ARCTUR in the questionnaire on legal issues (Annex I) as follows:

“In the development of CLASSICA, we primarily adhere to the CONSORT-AI and SPIRIT-AI guidelines due to their comprehensive framework for reporting clinical trials and protocol items in AI-driven interventions. These standards align closely with our project's objectives and methodologies. Additionally, we are actively considering and integrating relevant aspects from other guidelines such as DECIDE-AI, MI-CLAIM, MINIMAR, STRAD-AI, and TREE-AI, to ensure a thorough and responsible approach to AI in medical research and development.”

3.2.4 Conformity assessment procedures

Once all the requirements of the MDR are satisfied and necessary documentation is prepared, the manufacturer may apply for a conformity assessment to a notified body. Notified bodies are private entities, which have been designated by national authorities to conduct conformity assessments.

The type of conformity assessment required varies by the device's risk class, with several options potentially available for certain classes (Figure 7). The most practical route for medical device software that falls into class IIa is a conformity assessment under Annex IX, which involves a notified body audit of the quality management system and notified body's evaluation of the technical documentation [32]. If the outcome of the conformity assessment is positive, the manufacturer can draw up a declaration of conformity, label the product with the CE marking (Article 10(6)) and start marketing and selling the device in the EU..

Figure 7. Selected conformity assessment routes. This figure has been published in de Monte et al. 2021 [32] under the terms of the Creative Commons CC0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/public-domain/cc0/>).

3.3 EU AI Act

3.3.1 Introduction

The AI Act, a new EU regulation approved by the European Parliament in March 2024, will enter into force in mid-2024 - 20 days after its publication in the *Official Journal of the European Union*, which is expected in June 2024. The AIA will become fully applicable two years after entry into force (i.e., in mid-2026), with certain exceptions. Obligations for high-risk systems, such as medical AI systems will apply 36 months after entry into force (Article 113(c))⁵. Importantly, the AIA will not apply to medical AI systems placed on the market before the general date of applicability (approximately mid-2026), unless significant changes are introduced in the designs of the systems after that date (Article 111(2)). Consequently, if the CLASSICA system is placed on the market before mid-2026, the compliance with the AIA will not be required. At this moment it is uncertain when the CLASSICA system will be placed on the market. Hence, it may be worth to consider the requirements of the AIA in the CLASSICA project.

The AIA will apply to AI systems (including medical AI) that meet the following definition:

“‘AI system’ is a machine-based system designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments” (Article 3(1)).

The CLASSICA system meets this definition and, therefore, falls into the scope of the AIA.

Under the AIA the CLASSICA system would be qualified as a high-risk system since it falls into the scope of the MDR and requires a third-party conformity assessment (Article 6(1)). Consequently, it would have to meet a set of requirements of the AIA aimed at such systems. Compliance with both the MDR and AIA would be assessed through a single conformity assessment by a notified body with requisite competence.

The impact of the AIA on medical AI devices will be discussed in a UCPH publication, which is under review at the time of writing this deliverable. Below, we briefly discuss the impact of the AIA on the issues of bias, transparency, and continuous-learning AI systems, which have been highlighted in the DoA.

3.3.2 Bias

Article 10 of the AIA includes requirements for datasets used to train, validate and test an AI system. Article 10(2) lists data governance and management practices “appropriate for the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system” to which these datasets should be subjected. These concern, among other things, data collection practices, “relevant data-preparation processing operations, such as annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation” and importantly, the examination in the view of possible biases. More specifically, this examination should focus on possible biases that “are likely to affect the health and safety of persons, have a negative impact on fundamental rights or lead to discrimination prohibited under Union law, especially where data

⁵ Articles and recitals in Chapter 3.3 refer to the AIA unless specified otherwise.

outputs influence inputs for future operations” (Article 10(2)(f)). Subsequent point of Article 10(2) states that appropriate measures should be taken to “detect, prevent, and mitigate possible biases identified according to point f”).

The impact of these provisions on medical AI systems, including CLASSICA will be addressed in future publications (Task 8.4).

3.3.3 Transparency and interpretability

Recital 27 of the AI Act states that

“[t]ransparency means that AI systems are developed and used in a way that allows appropriate traceability and explainability, while making humans aware that they communicate or interact with an AI system, as well as duly informing deployers of the capabilities and limitations of that AI system and affected persons about their rights.”

The obligation of the providers of AI systems to inform the persons interacting with an AI system about this fact (unless it is obvious) is outlined in Article 50.

Interpretability, which in the provisions of the AIA is related to transparency, is addressed in Article 13:

“High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable deployers to interpret a system’s output and use it appropriately. An appropriate type and degree of transparency shall be ensured with a view to achieving compliance with the relevant obligations of the provider and deployer set out in Section 3.” Article 13(1)

Relatedly, the instruction for the use of the AI system, when applicable, must include “the technical capabilities and characteristics of the high-risk AI system to provide information that is relevant to explain its output” and “information to enable deployers to interpret the output of the high-risk AI system and use it appropriately” (Article 13(3)(b)) as well as “the human oversight measures [...], including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of the high-risk AI systems by the deployers” (Article 13(3)(d)).

The CLASSICA system is considered transparent and explainable [33]. However, these issues require further research in light of the relevant provisions of the AIA. This may be addressed in our future publications.

3.3.4 Continuous-learning systems

Article 43 specifies that

“High-risk AI systems that have already been subject to a conformity assessment procedure shall undergo a new conformity assessment procedure in the event of a substantial modification, regardless of whether the modified system is intended to be further distributed or continues to be used by the current deployer.

For high-risk AI systems that continue to learn after being placed on the market or put into service, changes to the high-risk AI system and its performance that have been predetermined by the provider at the moment of the initial conformity assessment and are part of the information contained in the technical documentation referred to in point 2(f) of Annex IV, shall not constitute a substantial modification.”

Consequently, continuous-learning medical AI systems may be placed on the market under the AI Act, provided that the above-mentioned conditions are met.

For now, the CLASSICA system is developed as a “locked” system, which will not continue to learn after being placed on the market.

4 Impact & Conclusion

This deliverable may help developers of medical AI systems to navigate the complex regulatory framework for medical AI systems.

The GDPR is particularly relevant to WP1 of the CLASSICA project, which focuses on the AI system refinement and support and WP4, which aims to clinically validate the CLASSICA system. Large amounts of personal data concerning health are processed in both work packages. The analysis of the requirements of the GDPR and their implementation in the CLASSICA project highlights the importance of:

- correctly determining whether the processed data are anonymised (and, therefore, outside the scope of the GDPR) or pseudonymised (and fall into the scope of the GDPR);
- choosing adequate legal grounds for the data processing and meeting related requirements (e.g., conditions for valid consent); and
- defining the roles of the partners (e.g., joint controllership) and fulfilling the obligations that these roles entail (e.g., conducting the DPIA).

The requirements of the MDR described in this report are applicable to WP1, since it is developing medical device software intended for future market placement and WP4, which aims to clinically evaluate the software. The analysis of the MDR and its implementation in the CLASSICA project highlights the importance of:

- correctly determining the risk class of the software and its status (medical device in its own right or an integral component or part of a hardware device);
- identifying and implementing relevant harmonised standards to ensure the compliance with the MDR;
- determining, which studies qualify as clinical investigation under the MDR and fulfilling the requirements for clinical investigation, which include preparing the documentation and obtaining approvals from national authorities, among other things;
- following the guidelines for clinical evaluation of medical device software to ensure that the studies are of adequate methodological quality and can be used to assess the compliance with the safety and performance requirements of the MDR.

The AIA is expected to enter into force in mid-2024. The requirements pertaining to medical AI systems will apply 36 months after the date of entry into force. Importantly, the AIA will not apply to medical AI systems placed on the market before mid-2026 (24 months from entry into force), unless substantial changes are introduced to those systems after that date. Consequently, if the CLASSICA system is placed on the market before mid-2026, compliance with the AIA will not be required. At this moment, it is uncertain when the CLASSICA system will be placed on the market. Hence, it may be worth to consider the requirements of the AIA in the CLASSICA project, for example, provisions related to data quality, bias, and transparency.

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Annex I

CLASSICA 8.1 Questionnaire, UCPH and PSU teams

Instruction for the partners

The aim of this questionnaire is to **provide the UCPH and PSU teams with information** needed to **complete the task 8.1**. In task 8.1 we describe the regulatory landscape relevant to the development and future commercialization of the CLASSICA tool. The results of that analysis will be relevant to the task 2.4 focussed on the regulatory interactions and requirements.

We would like you to **focus on the “key questions”**. We need the answers to these questions to address the specific context of the CLASSICA tool in the task 8.1. “Supplemental questions” are also relevant to the task 8.1 or the other tasks in WP8 and may help us to develop future publications. If you are able to answer them now, we would very much appreciate that.

Please be as specific as possible in your answers and consult your legal teams as needed. If answering these questions poses any problems (e.g., it is unclear if or how given provisions of a regulation apply to the CLASSICA), please describe these issues in your answers or **let us know if you want to discuss them with us**. We may be able to research them and share with you relevant existing guidance documents or publications.

Please send your answers to Emilia (eni@jur.ku.dk) **by 17 Nov**.

Key questions

1. What is the risk class of the CLASSICA tool?

Explanation: In order to place the CLASSICA tool on the market, it must comply with the Medical Device Regulation, which, among other things, requires us to identify the device’s risk class. The risks classes for medical device software are defined in Rule 11, section 6.3, Annex VIII of the MDR:

“Software intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa, except if such decisions have an impact that may cause:

- *death or an irreversible deterioration of a person's state of health, in which case it is in class III; or*
- *a serious deterioration of a person's state of health or a surgical intervention, in which case it is classified as class IIb.*

Software intended to monitor physiological processes is classified as class IIa, except if it is intended for monitoring of vital physiological parameters, where the nature of variations of those parameters is such that it could result in immediate danger to the patient, in which case it is classified as class IIb.

All other software is classified as class I.”

2. Are you using (or going to use) any harmonized standards? If so, which ones.

Explanation: Harmonized standards include solutions and technical details that support the essential requirements included in the MDR. The full list of the standards relevant to the MDR can be found

[here](#). (Note that some of them are yet to be revised or drafted to satisfy the requirements of the MDR). The use of standards is voluntary; however, as stated in Article 8 of the MDR “[d]evices that are in conformity with the relevant harmonised standards, or the relevant parts of those standards (...) shall be presumed to be in conformity with the requirements of this Regulation covered by those standards or parts thereof.” For further information, see the Medical Device Coordination Group [guideline](#) 2021-5.

Standards that seem to be relevant to the CLASSICA tool (non-exhaustive list):

- EN ISO 13485:2016/A11:2021 Standard for a Quality Management System for the design and manufacture of medical devices
- EN ISO 14971:2019/A11:2021 Medical devices – Application of risk management to medical devices
- *EN 62366-1:2015+AC:2015+AC:2016+A1:2020
Medical devices - Application of usability engineering to medical devices
- *ISO 14155:2020 Clinical investigation of medical devices for human subjects — Good clinical practice
- *EN 62304:2006+A1:2015 Medical device software - Software life-cycle processes
- *EN 82304-1:2017 Health Software - Part 1: General requirements for product safety

*These standards are yet to be revised to satisfy the requirements of the MDR. For a full list of standards that have already been deemed to satisfy the respective requirements of the MDR see [here](#).

3. Are you processing or going to process any personal data (as defined in the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR) for the purpose of research and development of the CLASSICA tool? If so, what personal data?

Explanation: Personal data means any information relating to a data subject (GDPR Art. 4.1). Data subject means a natural person who is identified or who can be identified directly or indirectly “by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person” (GDPR Art. 4.1). The GDPR does not apply to anonymous data, that is, data which are irreversibly deidentified meaning that they cannot be linked back to a person when taking into account “all the means reasonably likely to be used” as explained in Recital 26 of the GDPR. Further explanation of anonymization may be found, for example, in the [Guidelines 04/2020](#) of the European Data Protection Board (p. 5-6).

4. If you are processing or are going to process personal data for research and development purposes, what are the legal bases for the processing?

Explanation: There are five bases upon which personal data processing can be based under the GDPR: (1) consent, (2) contract, (3) legal obligation, (4) vital interest of natural person, (5) public interest or official authority, and (6) legitimate interest of entity or third party. (GDPR Art. 6; DPA Art. 5). Personal health data fall into the category of sensitive data under the GDPR. The legal bases for the processing of such data are specified in Article 9(2), which should be read in conjunction with Article 6. Art. 9 of the GDPR prohibits the processing of special categories of data except in the following cases:

- (1) explicit consent;
- (2) employment social security, or social protection;
- (3) vital interests of a natural person incapable of providing consent;
- (4) when data subject makes the data public;
- (5) substantial public interest;
- (6) healthcare;
- (7) public health; and
- (8) archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes. The EDPB defines “scientific research” as “a research project set up in accordance with relevant sector- related methodological and ethical standards, in conformity with good practice.”

5. If you use (or are going to use) anonymized data, at what stage are they anonymized and by whom?

Explanation: The process of data anonymisation involves processing of personal data and therefore should comply with the GDPR requirements.

6. Please describe the training datasets you use.

- a. What categories of data do they contain?
- b. What is the source of this data?
- c. Are all the data that you collect for training necessary for training the algorithm? Is there any category of data that you might be able to leave out?
- d. What are the characteristics of the patient population that you are getting training data from?

7. Please answer the following questions regarding the AI system that the CLASSICA tool will use to analyse surgical video and provide lesion classifications with confidence scores:

- a. Does the model use machine learning?
- b. Does the model use a linear model?
- c. Does the model use deep learning?
- d. Is the model interpretable?
- e. Is the model explainable?
- f. Will the model be locked or adaptive?

Explanation: It is important to accurately describe the type of AI system that CLASSICA will use to truly understand the legal implications for its use. For clarity, we are defining the relevant terms as follows:

- Machine Learning = subset of AI that allows algorithms to learn by using data and experience to improve performance.
- Linear Model = a model that uses a linear function to model the relationship between input and output variables. It can generate a transparent decision tree that describes the AI's logic by providing users with the actual factors it considered and the weight that it assigned to each factor.
- Deep Learning = subset of machine learning. Deep learning algorithms are trained to recognize patterns in data and make predictions, decisions, or recommendations based on those patterns by using several layers of artificial neural networks designed to mimic the human brain's decision-making process.
- Locked = a system that will always produce the same output in response to the same input.
- Adaptive = a system that can continue to learn as it collects new data while in use.
- Explainable = a system that relies on a second explanatory algorithm that approximates the output of the black box and makes post hoc explanations of the AI's output
- Interpretable = a system that uses a transparent and understandable reasoning process to provide an output

Supplemental questions

8. Are you using (or going to use) any guidelines issued by the Medical Device Coordination Group?

Explanation: The list of the guidelines is available [here](#). The guidelines are not legally binding, but as stated on the above-mentioned website "[t]hey present a common understanding of how the MDR and IVDR should be applied in practice aiming at an effective and harmonised implementation of the legislation." Guidance documents that seem to be relevant to the CLASSICA include "Guidance on **clinical evaluation (MDR) / Performance evaluation (IVDR) of medical device software**" ([MDCG 2020-1](#)) and "Qualification and classification of software - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 and Regulation (EU) 2017/746" ([MDCG 2019-11](#)).

9. Does the CLASSICA system satisfy the definition below:

"a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that can, for explicit or implicit objectives, generate outputs such as predictions, recommendations, or decisions, that influence physical or virtual environments"?

Explanation: This definition of AI is used in the EU proposal for the AI Act. The final version of the AI Act has not been adopted yet; it is not applicable law at this point.

- 10. In your view, are the training datasets you use:**
- relevant?
 - sufficiently representative?
 - appropriately vetted for errors?
 - as complete as possible in view of the intended purpose?

Would satisfying these requirements pose any challenges to you (practical, interpretative or any others)?

Explanation: This wording is taken from the EU proposal for the AI Act. The final version of the AI Act has not been adopted yet; it is not applicable law at this point. In this question we would like to know whether these requirements seem feasible to you and whether you see any challenges in satisfying them.

- 11. Do you examine the training, validation and testing datasets “in view of possible biases that are likely to affect the health and safety of persons”? Have you taken “appropriate measures to detect, prevent and mitigate possible biases”? Would satisfying this requirement pose any challenges to you (practical, interpretative or any others)?**

See the explanation above.

- 12. Are you following any other guidelines or standards in your research and development activities within the CLASSICA? A list of guidelines that are potentially relevant to CLASSICA is below.**

Acronym	Full name	Publication
CONSORT-AI	Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials	Liu X, Cruz Rivera S, Moher D, et al. Reporting guidelines for clinical trial reports for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the CONSORT-AI
DECIDE-AI	Developmental and Exploratory Clinical Investigation of DEcision-support systems driven by Artificial Intelligence	Vasey, B., Nagendran, M., Campbell, B. <i>et al.</i> Reporting guideline for the early-stage clinical evaluation of decision support systems driven by artificial intelligence: DECIDE-AI. <i>Nat Med</i> 28 , 924–933 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01772-9
MI-CLAIM	Minimum information about clinical artificial intelligence modeling	Norgeot B, Quer G, Beaulieu-Jones BK, et al. Minimum information about clinical artificial intelligence modeling: the MI-CLAIM checklist. <i>Nat Med</i> . 2020;26(9):1320-1324. doi:10.1038/s41591-020-1041-y

MINIMAR	MINimum Information for Medical AI Reporting	Hernandez-Boussard T, Bozkurt S, Ioannidis JPA, Shah NH. MINIMAR (MINimum Information for Medical AI Reporting): Developing reporting standards for artificial intelligence in health care. J Am Med Inform Assoc. 2020 Dec 9;27(12):2011-2015. doi: 10.1093/jamia/ocaa088
SPIRIT-AI	Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials–Artificial Intelligence	Cruz Rivera S, Liu X, Chan A-W, et al. Guidelines for clinical trial protocols for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the SPIRIT-AI extension. Nat Med 2020;26:1351–63.
STRAD-AI	Standards for Reporting of Diagnostic Accuracy Study	Sounderajah V, Ashrafian H, Aggarwal R, De Fauw J, Denniston AK, Greaves F, Karthikesalingam A, King D, Liu X, Markar SR, McInnes MDF, Panch T, Pearson-Stuttard J, Ting DSW, Golub RM, Moher D, Bossuyt PM, Darzi A. Developing specific reporting guidelines for diagnostic accuracy studies assessing AI interventions: The STARD-AI Steering Group. Nat Med. 2020 Jun;26(6):807-808. doi: 10.1038/s41591-020-0941-1. PMID: 32514173.
TREE-AI	Transparency, Replicability, Ethics and Effectiveness.	Vollmer S, Mateen BA, Bohner G, et al. Machine learning and AI research for patient benefit: 20 critical questions on transparency, replicability, ethics and effectiveness. 2018.
-	Guidelines for developing and reporting machine learning predictive models in biomedical research: a multidisciplinary view.	Luo W, Phung D, Tran T, et al. Guidelines for developing and reporting machine learning predictive models in biomedical research: a multidisciplinary view. J Med Internet Res 2016; 18: e323.

Supplemental questions based on the EU High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence's (AI HLEG) Assessment List

The EU High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence's (AI HLEG) [Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence](#) can be used to formulate some questions regarding the project's AI system.

1. Could the AI system affect the human autonomy and privacy of individuals?

2. Are there measures to ensure the AI system's integrity, robustness and overall security against potential attacks over its lifecycle?
3. Could the AI system have negative, critical or damaging effects (e.g., to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?
4. Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system result in critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?
5. Are there measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment in which the system will be deployed?
6. Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial, or damaging consequences (e.g. pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?
7. Will the AI system be trained or developed by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?
8. Will there be in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle?
9. Will there be in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?
10. Is there a mechanism that allows for flagging issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?
11. Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?
12. Are there mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g. traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact)?
13. Can independent third parties audit the AI system?

Supplemental questions related to the Data Security Section

The GDPR as well as Articles 21 (2) and 23 of the NIS 2 Directive provide an excellent basis for measuring the security posture of information systems. The following questions will help in structuring the legal aspects of the security requirements of the project:

1. Will there be policy and procedure on the CLASSICA information system risk management?
2. Will security include incident handling and business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, logs and crisis management?
3. Will there be measures for vulnerability handling and disclosure, as well as basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training?
4. Will there be policies and procedures regarding the use of encryption, access control policies and asset management for the system?
5. Where appropriate, does the security aspect include using multi-factor authentication or continuous authentication solutions, secured voice, video and text communications, and secured emergency communication systems within the entity?
6. Will there be a procedure to notify the relevant authorities and end-users of any incident that significantly impacts the provision of the services rendered by CLASSICA?
7. Is there a plan to obtain EU cybersecurity certification for the CLASSICA system or a part of it in the future? If yes, what standards are considered in developing the system?
8. Is there a mechanism for end-to-end security for the system?
9. Will there be a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures for ensuring the security of the system and the data it processes?